

TO THE QUESTION OF THE LEGAL STATUS OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES

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Tbilisi, Georgia*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10594250>**Abstract**

The article is devoted to the issues of legislative regulation of the main components of the digital economy: cryptocurrencies, blockchain, and mining, their legal status, the specifics of their use, and institutional regulation are characterized by the example of such large countries as the USA and China. The authors also analyzed the cryptocurrency market of the leading countries of the world, based on which the advantages and disadvantages of using cryptocurrency as cash, an asset, and other property were identified. The reasons for the growing attention of the world community to digital currency are considered. The history of the formation of cryptocurrency is shown. The main events that predetermined the situation in the cryptocurrency market are considered from the point of view of various institutions of the leading countries of the world. The approaches of several departments regarding the cryptocurrency itself as a special type of asset, mining as a type of entrepreneurial activity, bitcoin as a tool for attracting investments, and blockchain as a technology are analyzed. In addition, the prospects for the use of blockchain technologies in various socio-economic spheres of life associated with both commercial use and state and municipal administration are considered. A positive position regarding blockchain technology was noted on the part of the main institutional players in the financial market. The reasons are identified, in connection with which in Russia, most likely, no obstacles will be created to improve the financial system. A possible scenario for the development of the crypto industry in Russia is proposed based on the experience of foreign countries in this area.

Keywords: Digital economy, electronic money, cryptocurrency, bitcoin, initial placement of coins, blockchain, mining.

Introduction

In the context of the ongoing global financial and economic crisis, a decrease in the confidence of legal entities and individuals in the banking system, and the high volatility of foreign exchange relations, alternative electronic money systems are becoming relevant [1, p. 58]. The most famous electronic currency bitcoin (bitcoin) is protected by a cryptographic coding system and therefore it is often called a cryptocurrency. Blockchain technology has inherent security at the database level. Blockchain is a distributed data storage system whose records cannot be faked. The concept of blockchains was proposed in 2008 by a certain Satoshi Nakamoto [2]. This concept was first implemented in 2009 as a component of the digital currency - bitcoin, where the blockchain plays the role of the main general ledger for all Bitcoin transactions.

Discussion

The crypto industry is developing rapidly, attracting enterprising entrepreneurs and a fairly large intellectual resource. The method of attracting funding to startups through the placement of new cryptocurrencies ICO (Initial Coin Offering), by analogy with the public offering of IPO shares (Initial Public Offering), has become increasingly popular in the world over the past three years.

Due to the diversity of approaches to new electronic systems existing in international practice, the authors set out to assess the legal status of the elements of the digital economy: cryptocurrencies, ICOs, blockchain, and mining using the example of such major world powers as the USA and China.

To achieve this goal, the authors of the article considered four main elements of the digital economy from

the standpoint of state institutional regulation of financial and economic relations, as well as key figures of government and business.

The legal status of cryptocurrencies, in particular the Bitcoin system, varies considerably from country to country. In several countries, operations with cryptocurrencies are officially allowed. Usually, they are considered as a commodity an investment asset, or money, and for tax purposes are subject to the relevant legislation [3].

The positions of different states regarding Bitcoin are divided, but in general, they fall into the following three groups:

1. Countries regulating cryptocurrency: Japan, USA, UK, Singapore, Canada, Hong Kong. The listed countries have already placed Bitcoin transactions in the legal field.

2. Countries that are on the way to regulating cryptocurrencies. Several countries are developing a regulatory framework to actively introduce digital currency into the economy (Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Colombia, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Cyprus, Denmark, France, Germany, Israel, Italy, etc.).

3. Countries that ban cryptocurrency. Countries that consider it illegal and are currently trying to ban or restrict its use: Bangladesh, Bolivia, China, Ecuador, Iceland, Indonesia, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Venezuela, Thailand, and Vietnam.

Consider the features of determining the legal status of cryptocurrencies and their use in different countries.

The USA. Consider the history and facts of the adoption of elements of the digital economy in the United States. In March 2013, the Financial Crime Commission FinCEN announced that transactions for the exchange of any crypto-currency for fiat money

should be regulated in the same way as transactions for the exchange of fiat money among themselves (for example, dollars for euros). Not only bitcoin exchanges but also exchange offices must register as financial service providers (Money Service Businesses) and report suspicious transactions to law enforcement agencies.

In official reports from the World Bank and the FBI, bitcoin is considered a “virtual currency”. According to the classification of the FinCEN Commission under the US Department of the Treasury, bitcoin is classified as a “decentralized virtual currency” [4]. The US Securities and Exchange Commission has decided to equate ICOs with securities. Companies that do not register the issuance of a cryptocurrency or ICO will be punished.

In August 2013, a judge for the Eastern District of Texas (USA) made the following decision. Since bitcoins can be used as money to pay for goods or exchanged for common currencies such as the US dollar, euro, yen, or yuan, then bitcoin is a currency or form of money.

On March 25, 2014, the US Internal Revenue Service issued guidance on the taxation of transactions with bitcoins and other virtual currencies. Miners who mine bitcoins on their equipment are also subject to taxation. The miner is required to include the fair market value of the mined cryptocurrency in his annual gross income.

The legal policy about cryptocurrencies in the states of the country differs. In the state of New York, licensing of the activities of persons involved in the circulation of cryptocurrencies is carried out, the license costs about \$5,000. In California, amendments to legislation approved earlier by the State Senate declaring bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies “legal tender” have been adopted. This law allows you to conduct any transactions in the state in any electronic currency, including bitcoins [5].

Thus, the United States has now institutionally recognized all objects of the digital economy and has begun to regulate this process by law, including in the field of taxation.

China. In contrast to the actions in the United States related to the legalization of cryptocurrencies, the Chinese government has become unable to regulate the new free world of cryptocurrencies, although its rate has risen significantly due to speculative demand for coins in this country. Let us consider how the state authorities of China regulate the issue of determining the legal status of cryptocurrencies and their use in different ways.

In 2013, the cost of Bitcoin increased by 89 times, which led to increased attention to the electronic currency from Chinese investors as an alternative means of payment. In this regard, the People's Bank of China (PBOC) imposed a ban on operations with Bitcoin by financial companies, including the publication of quotes, as well as insurance of financial products related to this cryptocurrency. According to Interfax, the NBK justified this ban by the lack of legal status of Bitcoin as a currency. At the same time, the ban did not apply to individuals who could use Bitcoin in Internet

transactions, taking on all the risks associated with the use of this means of payment [6].

The key event of 2017 was the ban by the People's Bank of China on holding ICOs for Chinese companies. In addition, the NBK ordered local ICO platforms and companies that have already issued tokens to return all funds raised [7].

According to the official position of the NBK, all ICOs in the state began to be considered illegal on September 4, 2017. In the future, the regulator intends to punish such violations. He was threatened with legal consequences, including for completed ICOs.

According to the Chinese National Committee of Experts on Internet Financial Security Technologies, as of July 2017, 43 ICO platforms were operating in China, 65 ICOs were completed by July 18, and the placement of tokens allowed companies to raise \$398 million [8].

The cryptocurrency market met the news about the ICO ban in China very negatively. According to Coin-desk, bitcoin fell in trading by 5%, and Ethereum lost 15% of its value [9].

The introduction of this restriction in China provoked a correction, the scale of which for Bitcoin reached 40%, but this did not last long. The introduction of barriers in a single country leads to the flow of capital to other markets [9]. This is what happened in this situation. Forex Club analyst Irina Rogova noted that Chinese traders switched to the stock exchanges of Hong Kong and Japan. As a result, trading volumes on the Hong Kong-based Gate-coin exchange jumped 24%. In addition, Japan began to host Chinese ICO startups [10].

On October 24, 2017, the 19th Congress of the National Congress of the Communist Party of China ended in China. As a result of the Congress, some temporary rules and regulations were canceled. Presumably, they included a ban on bitcoin trading [11].

Along with Beijing's actions regarding the closure of bitcoin exchanges and the ban on sales of tokens and ICOs, we note that China is striving to spread blockchain technology. Active work is underway to create a distributed registry, and the Ministry of Information Technology of China is also supporting the blockchain laboratory, which was created after the ban on the operation of cryptocurrency exchanges. In addition, bans in China are associated by several experts with the readiness of the NBK to issue its state cryptocurrency, as evidenced by the creation of a research institute for the study of cryptocurrencies [11].

Thus, the events taking place in the field of cryptocurrencies in foreign countries can serve as an experience for determining the status of cryptocurrencies and ICOs in Russia, since today there is no legal regulation of the bitcoin network and operations with cryptocurrencies.

The position of cryptocurrencies in Georgia. A characteristic feature of the state policy in the field of cryptocurrency in Georgia is that its course is combined with the positions of the ministry (Central Bank, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Economic Development, General Prosecutor's Office), which do not have that unified position.

At the beginning of 2014, the National Bank of Georgia will classify surveillance and virtual currencies as “surrogate money”, which will have the status of dubious money laundering and criminal activities. The National Bank considers the “cryptocurrency” a digital asset, and not a virtual currency, to be inappropriate legalization of cryptocurrencies on Georgian platforms [12], but does not deny or dispute the prospects for the development of detection technologies underlying it. The regulator is considering the possibility of creating a platform for the transmission of financial messages using its use, as well as creating based on national cryptocurrencies [12].

From 2014 to March 2016, the Ministry of Finance of Georgia recognized cryptocurrencies as “surrogate money” and tightened measures on operations with them. However, already in August 2017, the Ministry of Finance recognized participation in the payment of amendments to transactions with cryptocurrencies in connection with their active use and legalization in some countries of the world (USA, Switzerland, Japan) [5].

Conclusion

ICO seriously reduces the cost of the process of raising funds and speeds it up, and ICO also removes several barriers between investors' money and issuers and will serve to further develop the economy [6].

According to the President of the National Bank of Georgia, blockchain is such an explosive technology, the implementation of which is necessary. According to him, this technology is already being used by Sberbank to implement several processes.

According to the President of the National Bank of Georgia, it is unacceptable to create barriers to improve the financial system, but it is necessary to form regulatory measures. In this regard, the task of the Ministry of Finance is to develop a framework bill on the regulation of cryptocurrencies by the end of 2027. Also, the Government of Georgia and the National Bank need to change the legislation of Georgia on the regulation of public attraction of cryptocurrencies and funds through the placement of tokens (ICO) by analogy with the regulation of the initial placement of securities until July 1, 2028, as part of the Digital Economy program. In addition, the head of state instructed them to develop

requirements for the organization of "mining", and decide on its taxation and registration of miners [9].

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